

Mobile Learning and Instructional Mobile Applications

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Hüseyin Uzunboylu

(Near East University, Turkey
huseyin-uzunboylu@neu.edu.tr)

Ergun Gide

(CQUniversity, Sidney, Australia
e.gide1@cqu.edu.au)

Advancements in information and communication technologies have an influence in many domains of life. For instance, learning is beyond classroom environment. In the recent years, innovative developments in mobile devices have changed the nature of distance education and this has led to the emergence of most appropriate media applications [Soykan and Uzunboylu, 2015]. Therefore, use of mobile learning, mobile devices and mobile applications increase day by day. [Cavus and Al-Momani 2011] described m-learning as a type of learning which uses digital mobile phone, personal digital assistant and laptops. Mobile applications used in learning process could be found in the existing market or new ones could be developed [Ozdamli and Turan, 2017]. Similar with the development of traditional desktop mobile applications, teamwork is required in this process as well.

Mobile learning enables students to share their ideas on developing internet technologies and work together. In addition, for the developers of mobile learning, it is important to accept mobile learning. Adopting mobile learning is an important factor to determine the learners and teachers of mobile learning to accept or reject [Hamidi and Chavoshi, 2017]. Based on the increase in the use of mobile devices, bring your own device (BYOD) approach has gained currency. In this issue, a scale development study was carried out on the effects of BYOD on workers and assessed its security components, benefits, applicability and sustainability (Murat Topaloglu & Dilek Kirar). A different scale development study was conducted on tablet-supported education (in this issue Murat Tezer & Fatih Soykan). Development and evaluation of a system aimed to promote the use of mobile and ubiquitous technologies in field trips were also studied in this issue (Edgar Marcal, Rossana Maria de Castro Andrade & Windson Viana). Mobile learning is commonly also used in language teaching and mobile applications are being developed for language teaching. In a study published in the current issue, an innovative Arabic spelling booklet into an interactive mobile game named as Afaneen was developed (Muna Saleh Al-Razgan). The game is designed for children 10 years old and above to enhance spelling ability. In a study related with language teaching, an innovative new m-learning scenario for listening comprehension assessment in an on-line test by implementing a multimodal audio learning source named binaural sound was examined (in this issue, Teresa Magal-

Royo, Jesus Garcia Laborda & Sara Price). Mooc's are other concepts which entered into our lives with mobile learning. Authors in this issue present the results of both the evaluation of the communication model and the student participation in open and mobile learning with sMOOC (Sara Osuna Acedo, Javier Gil Quintana & Carmen Cantillo Valero). Study fields on mobile learning increase and show change day by day. In a study in this current issue, open access studies conducted and published in 'Web of Science' indexed electronic journals and publications, as well as Master & Doctorate level open thesis studies from PQDT Open, OADT Org., EthOS and Council of Higher Education Thesis Center-Turkey on "web based/mobile teacher assessment" was investigated (Eser Çeker & Hüseyin Uzunboylu). Again, a study on the use of infographics in mobile supported education was also presented (in this issue, Hasan Ozdal & Fezile Ozdamli).

These realities have been illustrated in this monographic issue that we dare to call "**Mobile Learning and Instructional Mobile Applications**". The open call of this volume attracted a total of 28 papers, of which only eight (8) were finally accepted. Additionally, a total of eight submissions were accepted for publication from over 14 articles submitted for revision from the WCETR-2017 Conference: 7th World Conference on Education Technology Researches (Pristina – Kosovo 20-22 April 2017). Thus, the number of reviewers and researchers involved in this volume exceeds by far the number of those implicated in other similar volumes. For this reason, we would like to send out a special appreciation to members of the scientific committee. At the same time, we wish to express our gratitude to all the authors who submitted a paper in response to the call.

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